

YASHIL

**IQTISODIYOT
va
TARAQQIYOT**

*Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik,
ilmiy, ommabop jurnal*

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RIVOJLANTIRISHDA BUXGALTERIYA HISOBI,
IQTISODIY TAHLIL VA AUDITNING ROLI HAMDA
ISTIQBOLDAGI VAZIFALAR" MAVZUSIDAGI
XALQARO ILMIY-AMALIY KONFERENSIYA**

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EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS: IMPORTANCE, DEVELOPMENT AND IMPLEMENTATION

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Abstract: The article is devoted to the issue of introducing new approaches based on emotional intelligence in higher education institutions. The necessity of implementing emotional intelligence in higher education is substantiated. The interdisciplinary nature of emotional intelligence is revealed. The theoretical and practical foundations of emotional intelligence are explored. The benefits of integrating emotional intelligence into higher education institutions are highlighted. Specific directions for the application of emotional intelligence are proposed for students, teachers, and institutions themselves. The use of analysis and synthesis methods has made it possible to comprehensively explore the topic of the article.

Key words: emotional intelligence; higher education institutions; educational process; mental health; safe society.

Annotatsiya: Maqola oliy ta'lim muassasalarida emotsional intellekt asosida yangi yondashuvlarni joriy etish masalasiga bag'ishlangan. Oliy ta'limda emotsional intellektni tatbiq etish zarurati asoslab berilgan. Emotsional intellektning tarmoqlararo (interdisiplinar) xususiyati ochib berilgan. Emotsional intellektning nazariy va amaliy asoslari o'rganilgan. Oliy ta'lim muassasalariga emotsional intellektni integratsiya qilishning afzalliklari ko'rsatib o'tilgan. Talabalar, o'qituvchilar va muassasaning o'zlari uchun emotsional intellektni qo'llashga doir aniq yo'nalishlar taklif etilgan. Tahlil va sintez metodlaridan foydalanish maqola mavzusini har tomonlama o'rganish imkonini bergan.

Kalit so'zlar: emotsional intellekt; oliy ta'lim muassasalari; ta'lim jarayoni; ruhiy salomatlik; xavfsiz jamiyat.

Аннотация: Статья посвящена вопросу внедрения новых подходов, основанных на эмоциональном интеллекте, в учреждениях высшего образования. Обоснована необходимость применения эмоционального интеллекта в высшем образовании. Раскрыта междисциплинарная природа эмоционального интеллекта. Изучены теоретические и практические основы эмоционального интеллекта. Подчёркнуты преимущества интеграции эмоционального интеллекта в высшие учебные заведения. Предложены конкретные направления применения эмоционального интеллекта для студентов, преподавателей и самих образовательных учреждений. Использование методов анализа и синтеза позволило всесторонне исследовать тему статьи.

Ключевые слова: эмоциональный интеллект; высшие учебные заведения; образовательный процесс; психическое здоровье; безопасное общество.

INTRODUCTION

Education for sustainable development is interdisciplinary, inclusive, and continuous. Therefore, the introduction of innovative approaches to learning in higher education institutions is a necessary condition. Emotional intelligence (EI) is defined as a complex phenomenon, as the ability to work with emotions and demonstrate empathy. This concept has become an interdisciplinary category that is actively studied not only in personality psychology, but also in the context of education, management, sociology, and neuroscience. In the context of the growing importance of “soft skills,” emotional intelligence is considered a key factor in success in education, professional activities, social adaptation, and leadership. In higher education, EI research is gaining particular relevance, as it contributes to understanding the mechanisms of emotional self-regulation, interpersonal interaction, and the formation of psychological resilience of students [1–5].

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The methodological features of education for sustainable development are, first of all, the dialogic nature of the educational process, the active involvement of participants in the discussion of current problems, decision-making, and reflection, which allows increasing the level of emotional intelligence. Considerable attention is paid to the widespread use of active learning methods, such as project-based learning, discussions, debates, case studies, simulation exercises, etc. This approach is aimed at the formation of transversal (key, interdisciplinary) competencies, in particular: critical thinking, emotional intelligence, responsibility, environmental and social awareness, the ability to work in a team, and a systemic vision.

Theoretical research within this topic was carried out using methods of analysis and synthesis, which allowed generalizing scientific approaches to the organization of the educational process through the development of emotional intelligence for sustainable development and identifying key methodological guidelines for practical implementation in the higher education system.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Emotional intelligence in higher education institutions today plays an increasingly important role, as the modern labor market requires not only professional knowledge, but also social, emotional, and communication skills.

It includes the following components:

Self-awareness – understanding one’s emotions, strengths, and weaknesses.

Self-regulation – the ability to control impulses and maintain emotional balance.

Motivation – an internal drive to achieve.

Empathy – the ability to understand the feelings of others.

Social skills – effective communication, cooperation, and conflict resolution.

And especially now, when the excessive amount of information coming from various sources, digitalization, and computer addiction among young people cause a significant negative impact on psychological and mental health, which ultimately leads to various diseases and physical exhaustion. Therefore, the ability for self-knowledge and the capacity to be aware of and understand both one’s own emotions and those of others becomes important. These abilities are considered within the framework of the concept of emotional intelligence.

We have identified several useful provisions for the introduction of EI in higher education institutions:

Improving the educational process. Students with high EI cope better with stress, adapt to changes, and have higher motivation to study.

Developing leadership and team skills. In the modern world, it is important not only to know but also to be able to work with people: to lead, delegate, and negotiate.

Developing stress resistance and mental health. After the pandemic, full-scale invasion, and crisis of trust – the ability to manage emotions has become vital.

Improving the quality of the educational environment. Teachers with developed EI create a safe and motivating climate in the classroom.

Promoting the development of a safe society. One of the components of a safe society is psychological and emotional safety (a safe space for personal development and support for mental health).

And since the need to use EI in higher education institutions is obvious, the question arises: How to develop EI in higher education institutions? Having summarized the practices of using EI and the specifics of the educational process, we propose to work with students and teachers in parallel.

Thus, work with students should be carried out through the introduction of courses in social psychology, self-management, and soft skills, as well as through the integration of EI elements into disciplines: group work, reflection, and debates.

As for teachers, they should be trained in the development of emotional sensitivity, mediation, and empathic leadership, and provided with support in working with emotionally vulnerable students. Extracurricular activities, including coaching programs, student clubs for personal development, and the creation of psychological support centers in higher education institutions, will also contribute to the development of EI.

CONCLUSIONS

Emotional intelligence over the past decades has led to a growing interest of scientists in this phenomenon and has become a subject of scientific knowledge in psychological and applied sciences. The development of EI in higher education institutions is an investment in human capital, which ensures the successful integration of a graduate into the professional environment, contributes to social cohesion, and facilitates the formation of leaders of a new quality. In today's complex and changing conditions, the role of EI is growing more than ever, and therefore higher education institutions must in every way contribute to the development of EI and thereby provide the prerequisites for a safer society.

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